

Substitution of η_5 -Cyclopentadienyl Iron Carbonyl Halides by Diphenylcyclopropanone

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Substitution of the η_5 -cyclopentadienyl iron carbonyl halides $C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$ by diphenylcyclopropanone (DPCP) yields the complexes $[(DPCP)_3FeX][FeX_4]$; $X=Cl, Br, I$ in addition to ferrocene and $[\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2]_2$ as byproducts. The reaction mechanism is discussed in terms of normal nucleophilic substitution and a possible radical process.

AS an extension of our previous studies¹ of the substitution reactions of η -cyclopentadienyl iron carbonyl halides $\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$ ($X=Cl, Br, I$), the reactions of these compounds with the cyclic ketone diphenylcyclopropanone, Ph_2C_2CO , are reported below. Relatively few studies of the reactions of this nucleophile with metal carbonyl complexes have been reported although cyclopropanone metal complexes have been suggested as intermediates in carbonylation reactions of acetylenes². Complexation of the ligand in a η_3 mode was previously suggested by one of us in complexes of the type $C_2H_2COFe(CO)_3$ ³. However, such complexes have not been isolated although coordination via the double bond does occur in $(PPh_3)_3Pt$ (methylcyclopropanone)⁴. In general, however, it appears that DPCP which is highly polarized with a dipole moment of $5.14D^5$, most frequently complexes by coordination of the oxygen lone pair to form stable metal-oxygen σ -bonds. For example, Bird and Briggs⁶ isolated a series of complexes $(DPCP)_2MX_2$ ($M=Zn, X=Cl, Br, I$; $M=Co, X=Cl, Br, ClO_4$; $M=Ni, X=Br, ClO_4$; $M=Ru, X=Cl$). In all of these compounds, shifts of the infrared bands in the $2000-1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region are consistent with bonding of the DPCP ligand via the oxygen atom. In the complexes $\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2L$ (L =cyclohexenone and 3-methylcyclohexenone), nmr and X-ray studies confirm the presence of an iron-oxygen σ -bond in the bonding of the ketone to the iron atom⁷.

Experimental.

All solvents were refluxed over the appropriate drying agents, distilled and degassed before use. Reactions and work-up were carried out under oxygen-free nitrogen. Infrared spectra were recorded

on Perkin Elmer 457 and 283 spectrometers, uv/visible spectra on a Perkin Elmer 402 spectrometer, ¹H nmr spectra on Perkin Elmer R12B and Jeol PS100 spectrometers. Microanalyses were carried out in the microanalytical laboratories of this department. Conductivity measurements were made using a Radiometer instrument (Copenhagen type CDC 304). Linear plots of molar conductances versus (concentration)^{1/3} were extrapolated to infinite dilution.

$C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$ were prepared by literature methods $X=Cl^8$; $X=Br, I^9$. DPCP was prepared from dibenzylketone¹⁰.

Reaction of $\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$ and DPCP: A typical reaction is as follows: DPCP (8 mmoles) in 50 ml benzene was added to $\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$ (4 mmoles) in 50 ml benzene and refluxed for about 10 hr. Filtration of the hot solution, washing of the solid product twice with 5 ml cold benzene followed by *n*-hexane and recrystallization from CH_2Cl_2 -petroleum ether (40-60°) gave tiny crystals. The filtrate was reduced in volume to about 10 ml and chromatographed on a silica gel column and eluted with benzene. The first band (yellow) eluted was identified as ferrocene and the second band (red) as unreacted $\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$. If the reaction was carried out at about 60°, additional bands due to $(\eta-C_5H_5)_2Fe(CO)_2$ and $[\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2]_2$ were also obtained on chromatography.

Results and Discussion

When DPCP and $\eta-C_5H_5Fe(CO)_2X$ ($X=Cl, Br$ and I) were heated together in benzene under nitrogen, a microcrystalline precipitate formed

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within 30 min and on monitoring the reaction by infrared spectroscopy in the metal carbonyl region it was found from the decrease in intensity of the initial peaks [$\nu(\text{CO})=2057, 3013 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; 2054, 2008 cm^{-1} and 2044, 2000 cm^{-1} for X=Cl, Br, I respectively] that the reaction rate followed the sequence Cl > Br > I. In the case of both chloride and bromide, a band at 1969 cm^{-1} developed during the reaction indicating an intermediate since the final products contain no metal-carbonyl groups.

(nujol mull) identical with those reported previously¹². This compound decomposes to give (a) ferrocene and (c) the third compound isolated from the column [$(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2$]₂ the identity of which was proven by infrared spectroscopy. The formation of the above complexes by nucleophilic attack by DPCP on $\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2\text{X}$ with complete displacement of both carbonyl and cyclopentadienyl ligands under relatively mild reaction conditions is surprising, especially in view of the much slower

TABLE I—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA FOR [(DPCP)₃FeX] [FeX₄]

X	Decomp. Pt. °C	Colour	Analysis : Found (Calcd.)				Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})		Conductivity $\Lambda_m \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			C	H	X	Fe	2000-1500 region (a)	M-X region (b)	
Cl	188	Lime-yellow	59.16(59.50)	3.73(3.97)	19.92(19.56)	11.84(12.34)	1859(s) 1598(s) 1579(m) 1538(s)	383	122 ^a
Br	194	Dark orange	47.45(47.79)	2.44(2.65)	35.53(35.40)	10.00(9.9)	1857(s) 1597(s) 1577(m) 1537(s)	295	112 ^a 145 ^d

- ^a Measured in KBr discs
^b Measured in Nujol mulls
^c Measured in Nitromethane
^d Measured in Acetone

In general, reactant molar ratios of 1:2 (complex: ligand) were used and larger ratios simply increased the rate of reaction. The physical properties and analytical data of the complexes formed in this reaction (Table I) are consistent with their formulation as $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPCP})_3\text{X}][\text{FeX}_4]$ (X=Cl, Br, I) although in the case X=I the solid product was not sufficiently stable to give good analytical figures. The infrared data showed clearly the absence of any metal-carbonyl group; the shift of the higher frequency band in free DPCP from 1845 cm^{-1} to 1857-1859 cm^{-1} in the complexes and of the lower band 1618 cm^{-1} to 1598 cm^{-1} is typical of complexation of DPCP via the oxygen lone pair⁶. The far infrared region exhibited bands at 383 cm^{-1} and 295 cm^{-1} for the chloride and bromide respectively which lie very close to those reported for $[\text{NEt}_4][\text{FeX}_4]$, X=Cl, Br¹¹. The presence of the FeX_4^- anion was further confirmed from the uv/visible spectra of the complexes measured in acetonitrile; for example, the chloride complex shows a band at $\lambda_{max}=358 \text{ nm}$ compared with $\lambda_{max}=360 \text{ nm}$ for $[\text{FeCl}_4]^{-1}$. The ¹H nmr spectra measured in deuterated acetone showed clearly the absence of the cyclopentadienyl peak whilst the peak at $\tau=2.65$ (TMS as internal reference) may be assigned to the phenyl protons. The ionic nature of the complexes is further supported by their measured conductivities in nitromethane and acetone (Table I). The observed solid state magnetic moments of 4.1 and 4.0 B.M. of the chloride and bromide respectively (Gouy method) indicate some magnetic interaction between the two iron centres (in the solid state). Various byproducts were also produced in this reaction; thus, chromatography of the filtrate after isolation of the complexes $[(\text{DPCP})_3\text{FeX}][\text{FeX}_4]$, X=Cl, Br, I, subsequent elution and purification gave (a) ferrocene in yields between 20-40%; (b) $(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2$ which exhibited $\nu(\text{CO})$ bands at 2015 cm^{-1} and 1965 cm^{-1}

rates of substitution by phosphines and phosphites¹. However, the presence of an intermediate with a $\nu(\text{CO})$ band at 1969 cm^{-1} during the reaction suggests that halide substitution is probably the initial step with formation of $[\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2\text{DPCP}]^+$ analogous to that observed initially in substitution of $\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2\text{N}_3$ by tertiary phosphites and phosphines¹³. Further substitution then occurs with displacement of the carbonyl group and finally reaction with a second unreacted substrate possibly via a radical mechanism gives the complex and $(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2$. The formation of the tetrahedral $[\text{FeX}_4]^-$ is probably due to its formation from FeX_3 produced in the reaction by radical decomposition of the substrate although the above scheme must be considered speculative at this stage.

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